

ISic2916

I.Sicily inscription 2916

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Giddoni

2. s ðt(depositio) VI K(a)l(endas)

3. de(ce)mbr(e)s

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1909

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645305

Bibliography

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.

Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 579 fig.12

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 351
Pace, B. 1949. Arte e civiltà della Sicilia antica. Volume quarto. Barbari e
Bizantini. Rome, Naples, Città di Castello. At 136 fig.37

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2916. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4356418>